

Studies on the effect of added ascorbic acid and trehalose to tris buffered egg yolk extender on chilled ram semen

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Abstract

The objective of this experiment was to investigate whether the individual motility, live sperm and acrosome integrity percentage of chilled ram semen were affected by adding ascorbic acid and trehalose to tris buffered egg yolk. A total of 89 ejaculates were collected from 8 sexually mature Rahmani rams. Ejaculates diluted by tris based extender (control), tris + ascorbic acid (0.9 mg/ml) and tris +trehalose (50 mM). The diluted samples were stored at 4°C and examined at 0, 2nd, 4th and 6th days of chilling. Results showed that trehalose revealed a highly significant ($P<0.01$) improvement regarding the individual motility at 2nd and 6th day of dilution, as compared to TBE and TBE + ascorbic acid. Trehalose showed non-significant improvement in the percentage of alive sperms diluted by TBE+trehalose ($46.20\pm 2.38\%$) as compared to TBE, TBE+ascorbic acid (42.49 ± 3.09 vs. $39.69\pm 3.23\%$, respectively). Acrosome integrity at 4th and 6th day of dilution, improved highly significantly ($P<0.01$) in TBE+trehalose and TBE as compared to TBE + ascorbic acid. It was concluded that tris based extender supplied by trehalose (as antioxidant) revealed an improvement in chilled ram semen.

Keywords: Ram semen, egg yolk, ascorbic acid, trehalose, live sperm, sperm motility

Introduction

Artificial insemination with chilled- stored semen had become a technique in sheep breeding (Ax et al., 2000). The use of chilled-stored semen is limited by its relatively short time fertilizing capacity (Kheradmand et al., 2006). Oxidative damage of spermatozoa during storage is a potential cause of decline in motility and fertility during refrigerated storage of liquid semen (Ball et al., 2001). Efforts had been tried to improve the preservation of cooled ram semen by alteration of the extenders as well as the addition of specific components to maintain membrane integrity, prevent oxidative stress and/or preserve motility of spermatozoa in the ram (Sarlos et al., 2002). Addition of ascorbic acid to extenders could reduce the oxidative stress (Jian et al., 2010). Trehalose is a sulfonic amino acid, acts as a non-enzymatic scavenger that plays an important role in the protection of spermatozoa against ROS (reactive oxygen species), in case of exposure to aerobic

conditions and the freezing—thawing process (Reddy et al., 2010).

Material & Methods

The present study was carried out during the period from July 2011 to December 2012, in the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt. Eight sexually mature Rahmani rams aged 1.6-1.9 years and two mature Rahmani ewes aged 1.3 years were also used. Their average body weight ranged from 55-60 kg at the beginning of the study. A period of about 170 days before the beginning of the experiment was used for acclimatization of the studied animals. A general management program including deworming, disease prevention and hoof trimming was applied. Animals were apparently healthy and had apparently normal external genitalia. Animals were kept indoors in a covered shelter and allowed to walk freely. The females were separated alone from the rams using a special partition to prevent physical contact except at the moment of semen collection. The ration consisted of Egyptian

clover, wheat straw, yellow corn, wheat bran, broken horse beans, common salt and vitamins and mineral premix according to NRC (1985). Each ram received 0.4 Kg of concentrates. Water was offered ad libitum.

Experimental Design

I- Semen collection: Semen samples were collected by artificial vagina. A total of 96 semen samples were collected from rams throughout the period of the study. Immediately following semen collection, the collecting tube containing the ejaculate was immersed in water bath at 35 °C for 10-15 minutes until dilution.

II- Semen extension: -Semen was extended by three extenders which are:

A-TRIS-based extender (TBE) without antioxidant (control) and was prepared according to Salamon and Visser (1972).

B-TRIS with ascorbic acid (TBE+Ascorbic acid) (0.9 mg/ml extender) (SDFCL, Co., 54006K01, India) according to Ball et al. (2001) and Kheradmand et al. (2006).

C-TRIS with trehalose (TBE+Trehalose) (50 mM/100ml extender) (Sigma-ALDRICH Co., D-89555, Germany) according to Badr et al. (2010).

The rate of dilution with the previous extenders was 5µl semen + 95µl extender according to Ashrafi et al. (2011) and after gradual cooling; diluted samples were kept at 4°C till being examined. Diluted semen samples were assessed on days 0, 2, 4, 6 after dilution for the percent of individual motility, alive sperm and acrosome integrity.

Results

Table (1): Effect of added Ascorbic acid and trehalose to tris buffered egg yolk extender on sperm motility, live sperm percentage and acrosome integrity of chilled ram semen

<u>Days of preservation</u>	<u>Semen parameters</u>	<u>Tris based extender</u>	<u>Tris based extender + Ascorbis acid</u>	<u>Tris based extender + Trehalose</u>
<u>Zero</u>	<u>Individual motility (%)</u>	<u>84.13±0.56^a</u>	<u>84.48 ± 0.72^a</u>	<u>85.64±0.63^a</u>
	<u>Alive sperm (%)</u>	<u>77.40 ± 0.69^a</u>	<u>77.81 ± 0.64^a</u>	<u>76.68±0.58^a</u>
	<u>Acrosome integrity (%)</u>	<u>94.03 ± 0.88^a</u>	<u>92.60±0.50^a</u>	<u>94.56±0.40^a</u>
<u>2nd</u>	<u>Individual motility (%)</u>	<u>69.26±1.56^B</u>	<u>68.22±1.75^B</u>	<u>76.55±1.23^A</u>
	<u>Alive sperm (%)</u>	<u>69.42±0.88^a</u>	<u>69.99±0.95^a</u>	<u>68.83±0.85^a</u>
	<u>Acrosome integrity (%)</u>	<u>91.84±0.41^a</u>	<u>89.90±0.72^a</u>	<u>90.97±0.73^a</u>
<u>4th</u>	<u>Individual motility (%)</u>	<u>51.06±2.13^B</u>	<u>49.98±2.31^B</u>	<u>60.27±1.71^A</u>
	<u>Alive sperm (%)</u>	<u>59.06±1.42^a</u>	<u>57.52±2.13^a</u>	<u>59.21±1.60^a</u>
	<u>Acrosome integrity (%)</u>	<u>88.16±0.54^A</u>	<u>85.28±0.70^B</u>	<u>89.13±0.67^A</u>
<u>6th</u>	<u>Individual motility (%)</u>	<u>28.33±2.53^a</u>	<u>28.30±2.61^a</u>	<u>34.25±2.06^a</u>
	<u>Alive sperm (%)</u>	<u>42.49±3.09^a</u>	<u>39.69±3.23^a</u>	<u>46.20±2.38^a</u>
	<u>Acrosome integrity (%)</u>	<u>64.13±4.54^b</u>	<u>70.79±3.59^{ab}</u>	<u>77.61±3.04^a</u>

-Different superscripts between rows with small letters represent a significant difference at ($P < 0.05$).

-Different superscripts between rows with capital letters represent a highly significant difference at ($P < 0.01$).

N.B: Some semen samples were excluded from dilution because its volume was less than 0.75 ml and showed individual motility less than 70%.

-Number of diluted samples for each extender = 89

The mean individual motility at 0 and 6th day of preservation did not show any significant differences between the different extenders. A highly significant ($P<0.01$) improvement in the percent of individual motility was observed in diluted semen by TBE+trehalose at 2nd and 4th day of dilution, as compared to TBE alone and TBE + ascorbic acid. The mean alive sperm percentage at 0, 2nd, 4th and 6th day of preservation did not reveal any significant variations between different extenders. The mean acrosome integrity percentage at 0 and 2nd day of preservation did not reveal any significant variations between different extenders. While at 4th of preservation, the mean acrosome integrity percentage in samples extended by TBE+trehalose and TBE alone revealed a highly significant ($P<0.01$) improvement as compared to TBE + ascorbic acid. While at 6th day of preservation, the acrosome integrity percentage increased significantly ($P<0.05$) in TBE+trehalose as compared to TBE alone.

Discussion

Our results concerning the highly significant ($P<0.01$) improvement in the individual motility percentage of TBE+trehalose at 2nd and 4th day of preservation as compared to TBE alone and TBE + ascorbic acid were in harmony with those of Badr et al. (2010); Naing et al. (2010); Reddy et al. (2010); Toniato et al. (2010); Tuncera, et al. (2013) and Reda et al. (2015) who indicated that extenders containing trehalose showed a significant improvement in sperm motility. At the 6th day of preservation, results revealed a non significant improvement in the percentage of alive spermatozoa in semen diluted by TBE+trehalose ($46.20\pm 2.38\%$) as compared to TBE alone, TBE+ascorbic acid (42.49 ± 3.09 vs. $39.69\pm 3.23\%$, respectively). These previous results were nearly similar to those of Aisen et al. (2002); Bucak and Tekin (2007); Uysal and Bucak (2009); Badr et al. (2010) and

Reddy et al. (2010) who explained that addition of trehalose to semen extenders improved the viability of diluted ejaculates as compared to control ones. The improvement in acrosome integrity percentage at 4th and 6th day of preservation in ram semen extended by TBE+trehalose was in line with those of Hu et al. (2010); Badr et al. (2010) Tuncera et al. (2013) and Reda et al. (2015) who concluded that addition of trehalose to the extended semen improved the acrosome integrity percentage. Improvement of individual motility, viability and acrosome integrity percentage in extenders supplied by trehalose may be attributed to the fact that trehalose have several functions in sperm extender, including providing energy substrate for the sperm cell during preservation, maintain the osmotic pressure of the diluent, acting as a cryoprotectant and increase sperm membrane integrity (Uysal and Bucak, 2009 and Badr et al., 2010) and prevents the denaturation and aggregation of specific proteins at cold temperature (Kandror et al., 2002).

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